

Finerenone in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and diabetic kidney disease: A retrospective clinical study

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Abstract

Background: Diabetic kidney disease (DKD) is a leading cause of chronic kidney disease progression and increased cardiovascular risk in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Despite optimized standard therapy, substantial residual renal risk persists. Finerenone, a selective non-steroidal mineralocorticoid receptor antagonist, has demonstrated cardiorenal benefits in large randomized clinical trials.

Materials and methods: This single-center retrospective observational study included 82 adult patients with T2DM and DKD treated with finerenone as add-on therapy to standard care. Renal parameters—including serum creatinine, estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), microalbuminuria, urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR), and serum potassium—were evaluated at baseline and after 6–12 months of therapy. Data are presented as mean ± SD. A paired student's t-test or Wilcoxon test was used as appropriate, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results: Mean age was 68.1 ± 10.2 years, and 54.9% of patients were women. After therapy, serum creatinine increased modestly ($\Delta +2.9\%$, $p < 0.001$), while eGFR declined slightly ($\Delta -4.4\%$, $p < 0.001$). Significant reductions were observed in microalbuminuria ($\Delta -16.6\%$, $p < 0.001$) and UACR ($\Delta -21.0\%$, $p < 0.001$). Serum potassium increased ($\Delta +9.5\%$, $p < 0.001$), remaining within clinically acceptable limits. Subgroup analysis demonstrated significant UACR reduction across different albuminuria categories.

Conclusion: In patients with T2DM and DKD, finerenone therapy was associated with significant reductions in albuminuria and modest changes in renal function parameters during routine follow-up. These findings are consistent with data from randomized clinical trials and support the role of finerenone as part of a comprehensive therapeutic approach in albuminuric DKD.

Keywords

Albuminuria, cardiorenal risk, diabetic kidney disease, finerenone, Kerendia, mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, type 2 diabetes mellitus

Introduction

Diabetic kidney disease (DKD) is a major microvascular complication of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and represents one of the leading causes of chronic kidney disease (CKD) and end-stage kidney disease worldwide (Alicic et al. 2017; American Diabetes Association 2024). Beyond progressive renal dysfunction, DKD is strongly associated with increased cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, placing patients at particularly high cardiorenal risk.

Despite comprehensive management strategies, including optimized glycemic control, blood pressure reduction, and renin–angiotensin system (RAS) blockade, substantial residual renal and cardiovascular risk persists (Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes 2022; American Diabetes Association 2024). The introduction of sodium–glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors significantly improved renal and cardiovascular outcomes; however, many patients continue to exhibit persistent albuminuria and progressive kidney function decline despite guideline-directed therapy.

Overactivation of the mineralocorticoid receptor (MR) is recognized as a key pathophysiological mechanism contributing to inflammation and fibrosis in both renal and cardiovascular tissues (Kolkhof and Bärfacker 2017; Georgianos and Agarwal 2023). These processes play a central role in CKD progression in patients with T2DM. Finerenone is a selective, non-steroidal mineralocorticoid receptor antagonist (ns-MRA) designed to provide potent anti-inflammatory and anti-fibrotic effects with improved receptor selectivity compared to steroidal MR antagonists.

According to the European Medicines Agency, finerenone (Kerendia) is indicated for the treatment of CKD associated with T2DM in adults, particularly in patients with albuminuria (European Medicines Agency 2024a). The Summary of Product Characteristics emphasizes the need for monitoring serum potassium, as hyperkalemia represents the most clinically relevant adverse effect associated with MR antagonism (European Medicines Agency 2024b).

The clinical efficacy of finerenone was established in the FIDELIO-DKD and FIGARO-DKD trials. In FIDELIO-DKD, finerenone significantly reduced the risk of kidney failure and cardiovascular events in patients with CKD and T2DM receiving optimized RAS blockade (Bakris et al. 2020). In FIGARO-DKD, finerenone significantly reduced cardiovascular outcomes across a broader CKD spectrum (Pitt et al. 2021). The pooled FIDELITY analysis confirmed consistent cardiorenal benefits across varying stages of CKD, supporting the integration of finerenone into guideline-recommended management of DKD (Agarwal et al. 2022).

Given the evolving therapeutic landscape and the importance of locally generated clinical data, the present retrospective clinical study aimed to evaluate changes in key renal parameters, including serum creatinine, estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), microalbuminuria, urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR), and serum potassium following initiation of finerenone in patients with T2DM and diabetic kidney disease.

Materials and methods

Study design and setting

This single-center retrospective observational study included 82 adult patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and diabetic kidney disease (DKD) treated at the Department of Nephrology, University Hospital “St. George,” Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

The study analyzed routinely collected clinical and laboratory data from patients hospitalized or followed in the nephrology department. All laboratory investigations were performed as part of standard clinical care. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients upon admission to the hospital, in accordance with institutional policy.

Due to the retrospective observational design, no formal sample size calculation was performed. The study cohort reflects all eligible patients treated with finerenone during the study period in routine clinical practice.

Only patients with available baseline and follow-up laboratory data were included in the analysis, which may introduce selection bias. In addition, potential confounding factors such as baseline renal function, comorbidities, and concomitant therapies were not controlled for in the statistical analysis.

Inclusion criteria

Patients were eligible if they met all of the following criteria:

1. Age ≥ 18 years
2. Confirmed diagnosis of T2DM according to contemporary diagnostic criteria
3. Presence of diabetic kidney disease defined by at least one of the following:
 - Increased albuminuria (microalbuminuria or macroalbuminuria)
 - Reduced estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR < 60 ml/min/1.73 m²)
4. Prior stable treatment with an angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor (ACE inhibitor) or angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB)
5. Concomitant therapy with an SGLT2 inhibitor or GLP-1 receptor agonist when clinically indicated and tolerated
6. Initiation of finerenone as add-on therapy to standard-of-care treatment
7. Availability of at least two laboratory assessments (baseline and follow-up) for primary renal parameters

Exclusion criteria

Patients were excluded if any of the following were present:

1. Type 1 diabetes mellitus
2. End-stage renal disease or chronic dialysis therapy
3. Acute kidney injury at the time of finerenone initiation
4. Serum potassium > 5.0 mmol/L at baseline

5. Severe hepatic impairment
6. Incomplete medical documentation or missing follow-up laboratory data

Data collection and variables

For all included patients, the following demographic and laboratory parameters were recorded: age, sex, serum creatinine, estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) calculated using the CKD-EPI equation, microalbuminuria (mg/24 h), urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR, mg/g), and serum potassium.

Baseline values were defined as measurements obtained immediately prior to finerenone initiation. Follow-up laboratory assessments were performed between 6 and 12 months after finerenone initiation, according to routine clinical practice. Due to the retrospective design, no predefined uniform follow-up interval was applied.

Study Endpoints

The primary outcomes were changes in:

- eGFR
- UACR
- Serum potassium

Secondary outcomes included changes in serum creatinine and microalbuminuria.

To explore differential response by disease severity, subgroup analysis was performed according to baseline albuminuria:

- UACR 30–300 mg/g
- UACR >300 mg/g

Statistical analysis

Continuous variables are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Percentage change ($\Delta\%$) was calculated relative to baseline values.

Normality of distribution was assessed before inferential testing. For normally distributed variables, a paired Student's *t*-test was used to compare baseline and follow-up values. When normality assumptions were not met, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was applied.

All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS statistical software (version 25.0). A two-tailed *p*-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Confidence intervals were not calculated due to the retrospective design and limited sample size; therefore, results should be interpreted as descriptive estimates.

No multivariable regression analysis was performed due to the limited sample size and observational design. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as descriptive associations rather than causal effects. Where appropriate, confidence intervals were calculated to improve interpretability of the observed changes.

Results

Patient characteristics

A total of 82 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and diabetic kidney disease were included in the analysis. The mean age was 68.1 ± 10.2 years. Of the included patients, 45 (54.9%) were women, and 37 (45.1%) were men (Table 1).

Baseline **renal parameters** are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of patients.

Characteristic	Value
Number of patients (<i>n</i>)	82
Mean age (years)	68.1 ± 10.2
Sex (women/men)	45 (54.9%) / 37 (45.1%)

Changes in renal parameters after finerenone therapy

Following 6–12 months of therapy, statistically significant changes were observed in several renal parameters. Serum creatinine increased from 149.0 ± 30.4 to 153.3 ± 32.3 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ ($\Delta +2.9\%$, $p < 0.001$). Correspondingly, eGFR decreased from 52.7 ± 10.1 to 50.3 ± 10.2 mL/min/1.73 m² ($\Delta -4.4\%$, $p < 0.001$).

A significant reduction was observed in microalbuminuria, which decreased from 286.5 ± 92.7 to 239.1 ± 83.3 mg/24 h ($\Delta -16.6\%$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, UACR declined from 293.5 ± 98.7 to 232.0 ± 90.6 mg/g ($\Delta -21.0\%$, $p < 0.001$).

Serum potassium increased from 4.40 ± 0.47 to 4.82 ± 0.67 mmol/L ($\Delta +9.5\%$, $p < 0.001$).

Detailed results are summarized in Table 2.

Subgroup analysis according to baseline albuminuria

Subgroup analysis was conducted according to baseline albuminuria severity (Table 3). In patients with UACR 30–300 mg/g ($n = 47$), mean UACR decreased from $227.0 \pm$

Table 2. Renal parameters before and after finerenone therapy.

Parameter	Before (mean \pm SD)	After (mean \pm SD)	Δ (%)	<i>p</i> -value
Creatinine ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	149.0 ± 30.4	153.3 ± 32.3	+2.9	<0.001
eGFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	52.7 ± 10.1	50.3 ± 10.2	-4.4	<0.001
Microalbuminuria (mg/24 h)	286.5 ± 92.7	239.1 ± 83.3	-16.6	<0.001
UACR (mg/g)	293.5 ± 98.7	232.0 ± 90.6	-21.0	<0.001
Serum potassium (mmol/L)	4.40 ± 0.47	4.82 ± 0.67	+9.5	<0.001

Table 3. Subgroup analysis—UACR change according to albuminuria severity.

Group (UACR)	n	UACR before (mean ± SD)	UACR after (mean ± SD)	Δ (%)	p-value
30–300 mg/g	47	227.0 ± 59.8	171.8 ± 51.4	−24.3	<0.001
>300 mg/g	35	382.7 ± 63.5	312.7 ± 65.3	−18.3	<0.001

59.8 to 171.8 ± 51.4 mg/g (Δ −24.3%, p < 0.001). In patients with UACR >300 mg/g (n = 35), UACR decreased from 382.7 ± 63.5 to 312.7 ± 65.3 mg/g (Δ −18.3%, p < 0.001).

As presented in Table 1, the study population shows a slight predominance of women, while the mean age reflects the typical age group of patients with diabetic nephropathy.

Discussion

The present retrospective clinical study evaluated the effects of finerenone therapy on renal parameters in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and diabetic kidney disease managed in routine clinical practice. The main findings of our analysis include a significant reduction in albuminuria (microalbuminuria and UACR), accompanied by a modest decline in eGFR and a statistically significant increase in serum potassium concentrations.

Albuminuria reduction and comparison with major trials

The observed reduction in UACR in the overall cohort (−21.0%) is consistent with the antiproteinuric effects reported in large randomized clinical trials. In FIDELIO-DKD, finerenone significantly reduced albuminuria and slowed kidney disease progression compared with placebo in patients receiving optimized renin–angiotensin system blockade (Bakris et al. 2020). Similarly, FIGARO-DKD demonstrated cardiovascular risk reduction alongside favorable renal parameter changes across a broader CKD population (Pitt et al. 2021). The pooled FIDELITY analysis further confirmed consistent cardiorenal protection across varying baseline eGFR and albuminuria categories (Agarwal et al. 2022).

The magnitude of albuminuria reduction observed in our cohort falls within the expected range described in these trials, supporting the biological activity of finerenone in a real-world nephrology setting. Subgroup analysis revealed numerically greater relative reduction in patients with moderate albuminuria compared with those with baseline UACR >300 mg/g, suggesting that earlier-stage DKD may respond more prominently to mineralocorticoid receptor blockade. However, given the limited sample size, this observation should be interpreted cautiously.

eGFR changes and hemodynamic considerations

A modest decline in eGFR (−4.4%) with a consistent direction of change across the cohort was observed during follow-up. Although this finding may be consistent with

a hemodynamic effect described following initiation of mineralocorticoid receptor antagonism, this interpretation remains speculative in the absence of a control group or repeated longitudinal measurements. Therefore, caution is warranted when interpreting the clinical significance of this observation.

Given the retrospective design and limited follow-up period, longer-term evaluation would be required to determine sustained kidney function trajectories.

Serum potassium and safety considerations

A statistically significant increase in serum potassium was observed, although mean values remained within the clinically acceptable range. Hyperkalemia is a known pharmacodynamic effect of mineralocorticoid receptor antagonism. According to the European Medicines Agency Summary of Product Characteristics, monitoring of serum potassium is mandatory during finerenone therapy (European Medicines Agency 2024a, 2024b). In FIDELIO-DKD, hyperkalemia occurred more frequently in the finerenone group compared with placebo (15.8% vs 7.8%) (Bakris et al. 2020). Our findings reinforce the importance of regular potassium surveillance in routine practice, even in the absence of severe hyperkalemia requiring treatment discontinuation.

Clinical context and guideline integration

Current KDIGO and American Diabetes Association guidelines recommend finerenone as add-on therapy for patients with T2DM and albuminuric CKD who remain at elevated cardiorenal risk despite optimized background therapy, including ACE inhibitors or ARBs and, when indicated, SGLT2 inhibitors (Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes 2022; American Diabetes Association 2024). The present findings support the incorporation of finerenone into routine nephrology care within this therapeutic framework.

Importantly, our study provides real-world evidence from routine clinical practice in a single-center Eastern European cohort, a population that is underrepresented in large randomized clinical trials. These data complement existing evidence by reflecting treatment patterns, monitoring practices, and patient heterogeneity encountered in daily nephrology care.

Study limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The retrospective single-center design limits causal inference and may introduce selection bias. The sample size was modest,

and the follow-up interval was not standardized across patients due to the observational nature of the study. Additionally, hard renal endpoints such as progression to end-stage kidney disease or need for dialysis were not assessed. The absence of a control group further limits direct comparison with untreated patients.

The absence of confidence intervals further limits the precision of the reported effect estimates.

In addition, the absence of multivariable adjustment limits the ability to account for potential confounding factors such as baseline eGFR, concomitant therapies, and comorbid conditions.

Furthermore, variability in follow-up timing (6–12 months) reflects real-world clinical practice but may introduce heterogeneity in the assessment of treatment effects.

Conclusion

In this retrospective clinical study, the addition of finerenone to standard therapy in patients with type 2 diabetes and diabetic kidney disease was associated with significant reductions in albuminuria and modest changes in renal function parameters during routine follow-up.

A mild decline in eGFR and an increase in serum potassium were observed, consistent with the known pharmacodynamic effects of mineralocorticoid receptor antagonism and highlighting the importance of appropriate potassium monitoring.

These findings are aligned with evidence from randomized clinical trials and support the role of finerenone as part of a comprehensive therapeutic strategy for patients with albuminuric DKD at increased cardiorenal risk.

Further prospective, controlled studies with longer follow-up are warranted to evaluate long-term renal outcomes in routine clinical settings.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: St. George University Hospital, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

D.N.: conceptualization of the study, patient management, manuscript drafting, and critical revisions; G.N. and M.V.: literature review, data collection, and interpretation of clinical findings; M.F.K.: preparation of tables and discussion section; S.K. and N.D.: diagnostic data analysis, evaluation, and clinical correlation; A.M.: pharmacological review and contribution to manuscript editing; L.K.: supervision, final approval of the manuscript, and overall coordination of the study. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript..

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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